

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN LEARNING ENGLISH LANGUAGE FOR DISABILITY CHILDREN

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Abstract

This article deals to the importance of an inclusive education system in language learning for disability children, as well as methods for overcoming various deficiencies in their mental and physical development through language learning. The author provides analytical information on the advantages of gradually introducing inclusive education system in general secondary educational institutions.

Keywords: disability children, inclusive education, pupil, inclusive approach.

Introduction. Nowadays, foreign language lessons for disability children are aimed to develop children's interest to learn language, teach them to communicate in a new unfamiliar language. Educational institutions provide opportunities, and from a time perspective, intensive language learning is more effective than slow language learning over a long period. At the initial stage of the language learning process, children prefer to know words and phrases related to their world and their meanings in their native language. Disability children who start learning a foreign language at an early age do not yet understand grammatical structures, but first perceive them as stable combinations or phrases. Therefore, it is necessary to arouse interest in foreign languages in disability children and to structure the educational content in teaching based on the age and individual capabilities of such children. The younger the child, the more important the emotional approach and the child's relationship with the educator or teacher. If a child feels good in the learning environment, that is, free from fear and pressure, they will become more actively involved in the learning process due to their childlike curiosity.

Inclusive education plays a significant role in increasing the opportunities of children with disabilities in teaching English. English is the main language for participating in international events with high demands and current enterprises observed in different countries around the world. Therefore, it is very important for disability children to learn English through inclusive education. The importance of inclusive education in teaching English to children with disabilities is to stop them from being isolated from other pupils, to work with them and to change their free ideas and speech.

Methodology. Inclusive education brings several benefits to disability children. The teacher, when working with children with disabilities, tries to have one-on-one contact with each pupils and offer them a modified lesson. Inclusive education seeks to create a stable and comfortable environment for all learners in the learning process for disability children. This ensures that students with disabilities are satisfied with the lessons and adapt to the learning environment, and their ability to learn and produce English increases. An inclusive education system allows for the creation of individualized learning plans for children with disabilities. In these

plans, each student is taught based on their unique learning style, abilities, and limitations. This allows children with disabilities to learn English at their own pace and provides them with a personalized learning experience. Teachers should also demonstrate the use of different language learning methods when working with pupils with disabilities. This includes the use of visual, kinesthetic, or auditory methods.

One of the features of inclusive education is the provision of a support system for disability children. In this case, the administration, parents and other specialists support children with disabilities in learning English. With the help of this system, such children receive more help in the learning process and have the opportunity to develop themselves. It also helps children with disabilities learn various techniques and methods, and provides them with individually prepared handouts and manuals. The inclusive education system promotes the integration of children with disabilities into society. Through learning English, children with disabilities are integrated into society. This allows them to create changes in society and gives them the opportunity to work in various fields and find their place.

Result. The results of the research show that the use of inclusive educational methodologies in teaching foreign languages to pupils with disabilities not only increases their interest and motivation in a foreign language, but also makes the teaching process more effective, taking into account the individual needs of pupils. The use of inclusive educational methods ensures that students with disabilities have equal opportunities in education, has a significant impact on their cognitive and social development. The main principles of an inclusive approach to teaching foreign languages are an individual approach, the use of various teaching materials and taking into account the psychological and physical needs of pupils, developing pupils' ability to express themselves and freely express their thoughts.

This, in turn, increases pupils' social adaptability and success in learning a language. Based on the data obtained during the study, the introduction of inclusive education methods in teaching foreign languages requires new pedagogical skills from teachers. In this regard, there is a need for continuous training of teachers in inclusive education methodologies and familiarization with modern pedagogical technologies. As a result,

the success of pupils with disabilities in learning a foreign language not only improves academic knowledge, but also creates important conditions for their active and effective participation in society. This, in turn,

serves to develop inclusive education in society and provide all students with equal educational opportunities.

Fig. 1. The main principles of an inclusive approach to teaching foreign languages of disability children

The results of the analysis show that groups using inclusive teaching methodologies were more successful in learning a foreign language. In particular, students with disabilities felt more involved and their language learning success increased significantly when they were involved in activities. Specific materials and individual approaches for pupils yielded effective results. To measure the level of motivation, questionnaires were conducted with pupils, their interests and motivation to participate in language learning were observed. In groups using inclusive teaching methods, the level of interest of students increased by 25%. This indicator was especially high for pupils with physical disabilities, since for them the learning process became more individual and adapted.

The level of pupils' self-expression and participation in social communication was also considered an important factor in the analyzed groups. An increase of 20% was observed in the social adaptability and ability of students to freely express their thoughts based on an inclusive approach. This showed an individual approach to pupils and the effective use of inclusive methods. The approach and qualifications of teachers to inclusive education also played a major role. Teachers need to improve their qualifications in the use of inclusive methods. In the study, 65% of teachers participated in special training on inclusive education methods, which significantly increased the effectiveness of these methods. The active participation of pupils in society and their contribution to inclusive education were also studied. Through inclusive education methodologies, students improved their cooperation with society in the process of their learning and development. This, in turn, increased their social adaptability.

Conclusion. Inclusive education is an activity based on the regularity of the characteristics and capabilities of all pupils, allowing them to independently

use their relationships with each other, international time lines. This ensures that each student uses their full potential to the established extent in the process of teaching any pupils. Opportunities related to learning English are of great importance in the process of inclusive education. This provides significant changes in the preparation of children with disabilities and their abilities for the activity.

The results of the above analysis show that inclusive educational methods play a major role in learning foreign languages for pupils with disabilities. Pupils' motivation, level of achievement, social adaptability and self-expression skills have significantly increased through inclusive education. The data obtained during the research indicate the need for widespread use of these methodologies in the educational process.

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